

STUDY OF THE SPRING-IN PHENOMENON

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SUMMARY: Residual stresses always build up during the manufacture of composite components. In the case of channel or angle components, these stresses lead to a reduction in the enclosed angle. This phenomenon of the reduction in the enclosed angle is referred to as spring-in. To study this behaviour, sample composite angle components were fabricated from pre-preg tape and fabric, as well as from dry carbon fabric and resin using resin transfer moulding (RTM) technique. The effects of various factors such as ply stacking sequence, part thickness, tool angle, tool radius and tool material were investigated. In addition, comparison with the theoretical model developed by Jain and Mai [1] is provided and a good agreement is found.

KEYWORDS: residual stresses, spring-in, composite laminates, angle components, pre-preg material, resin transfer moulding, manufacturing

INTRODUCTION

Residual stresses are the internal stresses that develop during composite part processing. These stresses build up due to the shrinkage of the polymeric matrix around the reinforcement. The two main components that contribute to these stresses are: (1) the volumetric shrinkage of the resin during curing and (2) the mismatch in the coefficients of thermal expansion of the matrix and the reinforcement.

The most common residual stress effect observed in manufacturing composites is deformation of angled and curved parts after cure. In the case of isotropic materials, the configuration of a curved section is preserved and the contraction upon cooling is uniform. The change in shape of composite components upon cooling is therefore attributed to the anisotropic nature of the composites. For the case of a composite component the out-of-plane contraction is always larger than the in-plane contraction. This results in the two curved sides to approach each other and hence leads to a reduction in the enclosed angle. This change in the enclosed angle is referred to as spring-in [2-5]. This phenomenon mainly occurs because of the difference between the in-plane and out-of-plane strains in the plies due to the change in temperature and moisture content and resin shrinkage. Figure 1(a) shows the typical angle section. Figures 1(b) and 1(c) show change in volume in an isotropic material and residual stress induced distortion (in addition to the volume change) in an anisotropic material, respectively; the parameters ϵ_r and ϵ_θ are strains in the radial and tangential directions, and Φ_1 and Φ_2 are the enclosed angles.

Fig. 1: (a) Typical angle section (b) Change in the volume of a cylindrical segment of isotropic material. (c) Change in the shape of a cylindrical segment of anisotropic material.

Spring-in causes considerable difficulty and expense for composite manufacturers. Currently, tool angles are modified to compensate for part spring-in. The amount of modification is based on either “rules-of-thumb” from past experience or on trial-and-error. For angular parts, the compensation is normally between 1 and 2.5⁰. The most common problem found with using a standard factor is that the spring-in may vary with lay-up, material, cure temperature, etc. Therefore, what worked once does not necessarily work next time. In such instances, retooling may be required until an acceptable part is manufactured. If spring-in from residual stresses could consistently and easily be predicted, tooling could then be compensated for specific part characteristics without having to make a series of test specimens.

Therefore, the purpose of this paper was to validate the spring-in model developed by Jain and Mai [1] by fabricating some sample angle components. This spring-in model would enable the tool designer to predict the spring-in for a given part and thus assist with the tool design.

SPRING-IN MODEL

The model developed by Jain and Mai [1] analyses the cylindrical or the curved part of the component. The model includes the effect of resin shrinkage and also takes into account various factors that can affect the degree of spring-in such as tool radius, ply stacking sequence, part thickness, symmetric/non-symmetric lay-up, curing temperature, thermal expansion coefficients of the fibre and the matrix, enclosed angle and volume fraction.

The degree of spring-in and the residual stresses can be determined by solving the following constitutive equations [1]:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{yx} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{yx} \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \\ \\ \\ K \\ \\ \\ \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \omega_1 \\ \omega_2 \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \tau_2 \end{Bmatrix} - \begin{Bmatrix} N_x^T + N_x^c \\ N_y^T + N_y^c \\ N_{yx}^T + N_{yx}^c \\ M_x^T + M_x^c \\ M_y^T + M_y^c \\ M_{yx}^T + M_{yx}^c \\ M_{xy}^T + M_{xy}^c \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{T_{120}}{R} \\ \frac{1}{R} \left(T_{220} - \frac{T_{221}}{R} + \frac{T_{222}}{R^2} - \frac{T_{223}}{R^3} \right) \\ \frac{1}{R} \left(T_{260} - \frac{T_{261}}{R} + \frac{T_{262}}{R^2} - \frac{T_{263}}{R^3} \right) \\ \frac{T_{121}}{R} \\ \frac{1}{R} \left(T_{221} - \frac{T_{222}}{R} + \frac{T_{223}}{R^2} - \frac{T_{224}}{R^3} \right) \\ \frac{1}{R} \left(T_{261} - \frac{T_{262}}{R} + \frac{T_{263}}{R^2} - \frac{T_{264}}{R^3} \right) \\ \frac{T_{261}}{R} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where R is the mid-plane radius of the curved section, N_x , N_y , M_x , M_y , etc. are the force and moment resultants defined as:

$$[N_x, M_x] = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \sigma_x \left(1 + \frac{z}{R} \right) [1, z] dz, \quad [N_y, M_y] = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \sigma_y [1, z] dz, \quad (2a)$$

$$[N_{xy}, M_{xy}] = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \sigma_{xy} \left(1 + \frac{z}{R} \right) [1, z] dz, \\
 [N_{yx}, M_{yx}] = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \sigma_{yx} [1, z] dz, \quad (2b)$$

and

$$T_{ijm} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \bar{Q}_{ij} f(z) z^m dz. \quad (3)$$

The z coordinate is measured in the through-thickness direction with origin in the mid-plane and h is the total thickness of the laminate. The parameters N_x^T , N_x^c , M_x^T , M_x^c , etc. are the force and moment resultants from thermal and resin shrinkage strains. \bar{Q}_{ij} are the reduced material stiffnesses in the global coordinate system and $f(z)$ is the through-thickness expansion or the thickening term with contributions from thermal expansion, in-plane residual stresses and shrinkage strains. The K matrix may be regarded as the stiffness matrix. The various terms of the K matrix are given in Ref. [1]. σ_{ij} are the stress components and ε_x^0 , ε_y^0 , ω_1 and ω_2 relate to the mid-plane strains and κ_x , κ_y , τ_1 and τ_2 relate to the curvatures. The other details of the model and the assumptions involved may be found in Ref. [1].

With the use of appropriate boundary conditions and constraints, equation (1) has to be solved iteratively for mid-plane strains and curvatures since the thickening term $f(z)$ cannot be

determined unless the strains components are known. Once all the strain components are known, the degree of spring-in, $\Delta\Phi$, is simply given by

$$\Delta\Phi = \kappa_y R(180^\circ - \Phi) \quad (4)$$

where Φ is the enclosed angle.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

The test specimens were manufactured from unidirectional pre-preg tape and from dry fabric and resin transfer moulding (RTM) technology. The results for carbon/epoxy plain-weave pre-preg fabric were taken directly from an earlier spring-in study conducted by Lutton [6].

Fabrication of Pre-preg Samples Using Unidirectional Tape

These samples were fabricated from Fiberite T300/934 carbon/epoxy pre-preg tape and were cured at 177 °C. Both the male and the female components of the RTM tool (discussed in detail later) were used to produce these components. This allowed us to examine the effect of type of tooling on the spring-in. The following lay-ups were considered for this study: [0/0]_s, [30/-30]_s, [45/-45]_s, [60/-60]_s, [90/90]_s, [90/0/90/0]_s, and [0/90/0/90]_s. The first five lay-ups allowed us to study the effect of the orientation angle of the angle ply laminates. The last two allowed us to examine the effect of the lay-up sequence. In addition, three different tool radii were considered for the female tooling, 4, 7, and 8 mm, and two different radii for the male tooling, 3 and 6 mm. This allowed us to examine the effect of tool radius on the spring-in.

The nominal thickness of each ply was approx. 0.2 mm. The fibre volume fraction was approximately 65 percent and typical properties of a unidirectional laminate as estimated from micromechanics relations are given in Table 1. In predicting the cure shrinkage strains, the linear resin shrinkage during cure was assumed to be 1.5 percent. The parameters E, G and ν represent the Young's modulus, the shear modulus and the Poisson's ratio. The parameters α and ϵ_c represent the coefficient of thermal expansion and the cure shrinkage strain.

Table 1: Material properties of Fiberite T300/934 carbon/epoxy unidirectional laminate.

E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	E_{33} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
150.76	7.93	7.93	3.7	0.2525	0.2525	0.30

α_1 ($10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$)	α_2 ($10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$)	α_3 ($10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$)	ϵ_c^1	ϵ_c^2	ϵ_c^3
-0.8×10^{-6}	27.62×10^{-6}	27.62×10^{-6}	-0.125×10^{-3}	-0.7×10^{-2}	-0.7×10^{-2}

Fabrication of Pre-preg Samples Using Plain-Weave Fabric

These samples were fabricated from the Hexcel W3L282-42"-F584 material. The nominal resin content in the pre-preg was 40 ± 3 percent by weight, the fibre areal weight (density) was 193 ± 8 g/m² and the standard cured ply thickness was 0.19 mm. To study the effect of tooling material, three different tooling materials, namely, aluminium, steel and carbon/epoxy

composite, were used. In addition, to analyse the effect of the tool angle, four tool angles were taken into consideration: 45° , 70° , 90° and 135° . All the tools were male tools with a constant tool radius of 2 mm. The effect of laminate thickness was studied by increasing the number of plies. The lay-ups consisted of 4, 6 and 10 plies with the orientations: $[0/0]_s$, $[45/45]_s$, $[0/45]_s$, $[0/0/0]_s$, $[45/45/45]_s$, $[0/45/0]_s$, $[0/0/0/0/0]_s$, $[45/45/45/45/45]_s$, and $[0/45/0/45/0]_s$.

These samples were also cured at 177°C . The material properties for a fabric laminate (with 0° lay-up) as estimated from micromechanics relations are given in Table 2. Again, the resin shrinkage was estimated to be 1.5 percent.

Table 2: Material properties of plain-weave carbon/epoxy 0° laminate.

E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	E_{33} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
80.05	80.05	8.68	4.0	0.0275	0.2525	0.2525

α_1 ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	α_2 ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	α_3 ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	ϵ_c^1	ϵ_c^2	ϵ_c^3
1.73×10^{-6}	1.73×10^{-6}	44.42×10^{-6}	-0.6×10^{-3}	-0.6×10^{-3}	-0.9×10^{-2}

Fabrication of RTM Samples

These samples were fabricated from Ciba Geigy “uniweave” Injectex (GU230-E01) fabric and RTM6 resin using resin transfer moulding (RTM) technology. The uniweave fabric has 90 % 3K carbon tows in the warp direction and 10 % 1K carbon tows in the weft direction.

Steel was chosen to construct the RTM tool because of its relatively smaller coefficient of expansion. This would minimise the effect of the tool material on the spring-in angle. The tool used had two parts which are best described as male and female “V - Blocks” with a 90° enclosed angle (see Figure 2). The male part had a machined recess for an “O” ring seal and a machined, two-stepped rebate to accommodate the preform; one step was 1 mm deep and the other was 2 mm deep. The tool radii machined into the apex were 3 mm and 6 mm in the case of 1 mm rebate and 6 mm in the case of 2 mm rebate in the male part. Accordingly, the tool radii for the female part were 4 mm, 7 mm and 8 mm. Thus the components produced were 1 mm (with internal radii 3 mm and 6 mm) and 2 mm (with internal radius 6 mm) thick. Also, the male part had three resin outlets common to each of the three preform at the apex of the “V”. The female part had two off peripheral inlets.

(a) (b)
Fig. 2: RTM tool in (a) unassembled form and (b) assembled form.

The lay-ups considered for each RTM run were as follows: (1) [0/0]_s, [0/0]_s, [0/0]_{2s}, (2) [30/-30]_s, [30/-30]_s, [30/30/-30/-30]_s, (3) [45/-45]_s, [45/-45]_s, [45/45/-45/-45]_s, (4) [60/-60]_s, [60/-60]_s, [60/60/-60/-60]_s, and (5) [90/90]_s, [90/90]_s, [90/90/90/90]_s. The first two lay-ups for each run were identical with inner radii of 3 mm and 6 mm, respectively, and 1 mm thickness. The third lay-up had an inner radius of 6 mm and was 2 mm thick. The lay-ups considered allowed us to study the effect of the radius, thickness and the orientation angle of the angle ply laminates.

From the thickness of the laminate, the areal density of the “uniweave” Injectex (220 g/m²), and the density of T300 carbon fibres (1.75 g/m²), the volume fraction of the lay-ups was determined to be 50.3%. The resin cure shrinkage was estimated to be 1.5 percent. The laminate properties, determined from micromechanics relations, are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Material properties of “Unidirectional” carbon/epoxy RTM laminate.

E₁₁ (GPa)	E₂₂ (GPa)	E₃₃ (GPa)	G₁₂ (GPa)	v₁₂	v₁₃	v₂₃
106.3	16.67	5.44	2.43	0.09	0.275	0.275
α₁ (°C)	α₂ (°C)	α₃ (°C)	ε_c¹	ε_c²	ε_c³	
0.145×10 ⁻⁶	13.0×10 ⁻⁶	53.25×10 ⁻⁶	-0.32×10 ⁻³	-0.32×10 ⁻²	-0.12×10 ⁻¹	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The cure temperature for the pre-preg samples was 177 °C (350 °F) and for the RTM samples was 160 °C. The ambient temperature was assumed to be 21 °C.

Figure 3 shows the model predictions as a function of radius/thickness (R/h) ratio for all three composite materials considered in this study. It can clearly be seen that for (R/h) ratio greater than 1, the degree of spring-in remains constant and does not depend on the radius of curvature or the thickness of the laminate. For the lay-ups considered in this study, the R/h ratio was greater than 1. Therefore, while calculating theoretical spring-in values, only one R value was considered. It should also be noted here that although the cure temperature for RTM laminates was lower than that for the pre-preg laminates, higher spring-in angles are predicted by theory for the RTM laminates because of higher coefficient of expansion and resin shrinkage in the through-thickness direction.

Table 4 summarises the results for the Fiberite T300/934 unidirectional tape material. The parameter R_t in this table is the tool radius and R_i is the internal radius. It can be seen from this table that there is considerable scatter in the spring-in data. The spring-in data given for each lay-up is an average of three values, measured from a single specimen at three different places. The difference between the results from male and female tooling can be attributed to the matrix bridging observed in the components produced from female tooling. The matrix bridging could be defined as the accumulation of excess resin due to resin flow during curing at the corner of the component on the surface away from the tool. No matrix bridging was observed in components produced using male tooling. In the case of female tooling, both matrix bridging and a resin rich layer (on the tool side) were more pronounced for smaller tool radius (i.e. the 4 mm tool radius). For this reason, very large spring-in angles were observed for [45/-45]_s and [60/-60]_s lay-ups from female tooling for 4 mm tool radius. Also,

the amount of matrix bridging was not consistent in different specimens produced from the same tooling. In the case of thicker laminates, no noticeable matrix bridging was observed in components produced from female tooling and therefore similar spring-in results were obtained in components manufactured on both male and female tooling. However, in general, there was a lot more scatter in the data from female tooling for different tool radii.

Fig. 3: Effect of (R/h) ratio on the spring-in of a cross ply [90/0/90/0]_s laminate.

Figure 4 shows the comparison between theoretical predictions and experimental data for components produced using male tooling. The agreement between the two is not so good. This could have resulted from the difficulty in measuring the spring-in angles with good accuracy because the specimens were very thin and could deform quite easily while measuring the angles. However, for thicker laminates (8 ply lay-ups) shown in Table 4, the agreement between experimental data and predictions is excellent in the case of male tooling and is within experimental error in the case of female tooling. This verifies the validity of the spring-in model. It should also be noted here that the results for both [90/0/90/0]_s and [0/90/0/90]_s lay-ups are quite similar (for male tooling) and independent of the tool radii and thus indicate that for symmetric lay-ups, the effect of the lay-up sequence on the degree of spring-in is insignificant.

Table 4: Experimental and Theoretical Results for Unidirectional Pre-preg Material.

Lay-up	Male Tool		Female Tool			Theory R _i = 3 mm
	R _t = 3 mm	R _t = 6 mm	R _t = 4 mm	R _t = 7 mm	R _t = 8 mm	
[0/0] _s	0.2	0.75	0.57	0.68	0.73	0.0
[30/-30] _s	0.21	0.19	0.91	-0.24	-0.49	0.45
[45/-45] _s	0.88	0.70	2.94	0.96	1.38	1.11
[60/-60] _s	1.02	1.20	3.36	0.95	0.78	1.28
[90/-90] _s	1.15	1.24	1.29	0.40	0.42	1.023
[90/0/90/0] _s	1.23	1.26	1.05	1.0	1.02	1.233
[0/90/0/90] _s	1.20	1.28	1.37	1.25	1.40	1.233

Fig. 4: Effect of the orientation angle of an angle ply $[\phi/-\phi]_s$ laminate on the spring-in in the case of unidirectional pre-preg material.

Fig. 5: Magnitude of spring-in observed for the four ply lay-ups cured on aluminium tooling.

Fig. 6: Magnitude of spring-in observed for the ten ply lay-ups cured on aluminium tooling.

For the plain-weave fabric material, only male tools with tool radius of 2 mm were used to fabricate the samples. Figures 5-6 illustrate the magnitude of spring-in observed for the 4 and 10 ply aluminium tooled lay-ups. It can clearly be seen that ply orientation angles do not have any significant effect on the degree of spring-in. The theoretical predictions are also shown in these figures and a good agreement with experimental data (except for a tool angle of 70°) can be observed. It can also be seen that, in general, spring-in decreases with an increase in the tool angle. Figure 7 shows that an increase in thickness by increasing the number of plies does

not have any significant effect on the degree of spring-in. This is consistent with the theoretical predictions. The results for lay-ups cured on steel and composite tools were similar to those for lay-ups cured on aluminium tool and are therefore not shown in graphical form. Since the model predicts that for fabric laminates the spring-in angles do not depend on the thickness of the laminate or on the ply orientation angles, to provide comparison between tool materials, an average spring-in values for each tool angle was determined. Figure 8 shows the comparison between theoretical predictions and average spring-in angles for components cured on different tool materials. It can be seen from this figure that tool material has negligible effect on the spring-in angles. This validates the assumption made in our theoretical analysis that spring-in does not depend on the tool material.

Fig. 7: Spring-in observed for the 45° orientated ply lay-ups cured on aluminium tooling.

Fig. 8: Comparison between average spring-in angles and theoretical predictions.

Fig. 9: Magnitude of spring-in observed in RTM samples for different internal radii and laminate thicknesses for angle ply $[\phi/-\phi]_s$ laminates.

The spring-in results for the RTM samples along with the theoretical results are shown in Figure 9. The predictions are found to lie between the experimental results. The RTM tool

was designed to reveal information on the effect of tool radius and the thickness of the laminate on the magnitude of spring-in. However, from the experimental data it is not possible to identify any trends in the spring-in angles as a function of the internal radius (R_i) or the thickness of the component. Since theoretical predictions are independent of the internal radius and the thickness of the laminate, a comparison between average spring-in angles and theoretical predictions is shown in Figure 10 and a good agreement is found.

Fig. 10: Comparison between theoretical predictions and average spring-in angles for the RTM samples.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, spring-in model developed by Jain and Mai has been evaluated. Reasonable agreement is found between experimental results and theoretical predictions. Therefore, the spring-in model developed could be used to assist tool designers with the tool design. For radius-to-thickness (R/h) ratios greater than one, spring-in is found to be independent of the radius or the thickness of the laminate. In addition, it is found that the magnitude of spring-in does not depend on the lay-up sequence (for symmetric lay-ups) or the tool material, and that the spring-in angle decreases with an increase in the tool angle. In the case of fabric laminates, the orientation of the plies does not affect the degree of spring-in.

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Table 5: Experimental and Theoretical Results for Plain-Weave Fabric Pre-preg Material.

Lay-up	Aluminium Tool				Steel Tool				Composite Tool				Theory ($R_i = 2$ mm)			
	45°	70°	90°	135°	45°	70°	90°	135°	45°	70°	90°	135°	45°	70°	90°	135°
[0/0] _s	2.39 ⁰	2.03 ⁰	1.37 ⁰	0.66 ⁰	2.02 ⁰	1.90 ⁰	1.27 ⁰	0.61 ⁰	2.25 ⁰	2.12 ⁰	1.63 ⁰	0.67 ⁰	2.03 ⁰	1.66 ⁰	1.36 ⁰	0.68 ⁰
[45/45] _s	2.25 ⁰	2.17 ⁰	1.41 ⁰	0.69 ⁰	1.98 ⁰	2.02 ⁰	1.30 ⁰	0.45 ⁰	1.80 ⁰	2.03 ⁰	1.50 ⁰	0.62 ⁰	2.03 ⁰	1.66 ⁰	1.36 ⁰	0.68 ⁰
[0/45] _s	1.96 ⁰	1.98 ⁰	1.36 ⁰	0.58 ⁰	1.97 ⁰	1.87 ⁰	1.23 ⁰	0.58 ⁰	2.0 ⁰	1.9 ⁰	1.6 ⁰	0.7 ⁰	2.03 ⁰	1.66 ⁰	1.36 ⁰	0.68 ⁰
[0/0/0] _s	2.0 ⁰	2.34 ⁰	1.74 ⁰	0.95 ⁰	2.24 ⁰	2.36 ⁰	1.50 ⁰	1.05 ⁰	1.98 ⁰	2.02 ⁰	1.53 ⁰	0.53 ⁰	2.03 ⁰	1.66 ⁰	1.36 ⁰	0.68 ⁰
[45/45/45] _s	1.93 ⁰	2.08 ⁰	1.48 ⁰	0.79 ⁰	1.79 ⁰	2.15 ⁰	1.64 ⁰	0.85 ⁰	1.97 ⁰	1.85 ⁰	1.37 ⁰	0.53 ⁰	2.03 ⁰	1.66 ⁰	1.36 ⁰	0.68 ⁰
[0/45/0] _s	2.52 ⁰	2.05 ⁰	1.32 ⁰	0.60 ⁰	1.93 ⁰	1.94 ⁰	1.43 ⁰	0.68 ⁰	2.05 ⁰	1.97 ⁰	1.44 ⁰	0.63 ⁰	2.03 ⁰	1.66 ⁰	1.36 ⁰	0.68 ⁰
[0/0/0/0/0] _s	1.89 ⁰	1.97 ⁰	1.26 ⁰	0.86 ⁰	1.85 ⁰	1.77 ⁰	1.18 ⁰	0.84 ⁰	1.85 ⁰	2.02 ⁰	1.50 ⁰	0.55 ⁰	2.03 ⁰	1.66 ⁰	1.36 ⁰	0.68 ⁰
[45/45/45/45/45] _s	1.83 ⁰	2.03 ⁰	1.20 ⁰	1.00 ⁰	1.82 ⁰	1.80 ⁰	1.41 ⁰	1.03 ⁰	1.59 ⁰	1.57 ⁰	1.28 ⁰	0.63 ⁰	2.03 ⁰	1.66 ⁰	1.36 ⁰	0.68 ⁰
[0/45/0/45/0] _s	2.02 ⁰	1.84 ⁰	1.33 ⁰	0.91 ⁰	1.35 ⁰	1.90 ⁰	1.07 ⁰	0.77 ⁰	1.57 ⁰	1.87 ⁰	1.18 ⁰	0.70 ⁰	2.03 ⁰	1.66 ⁰	1.36 ⁰	0.68 ⁰
Average	2.09 ⁰	2.05 ⁰	1.39 ⁰	0.78 ⁰	1.88 ⁰	1.97 ⁰	1.34 ⁰	0.76 ⁰	1.89 ⁰	1.93 ⁰	1.45 ⁰	0.62 ⁰	2.03 ⁰	1.66 ⁰	1.36 ⁰	0.68 ⁰

Table 6: Experimental and Theoretical Results for RTM Samples.

Lay-up	R_i (mm)	RTM Tool (Exptl.)	Theory
[0/0] _s	3.0	1.81 ⁰	1.30 ⁰
[0/0] _s	6.0	0.91 ⁰	1.30 ⁰
[0/0/0/0] _s	6.0	0.76 ⁰	1.30 ⁰
[30/-30] _s	3.0	0.63 ⁰	1.30 ⁰
[30/-30] _s	6.0	1.36 ⁰	1.30 ⁰
[30/30/-30/-30] _s	6.0	0.81 ⁰	1.30 ⁰
[45/-45] _s	3.0	1.66 ⁰	1.69 ⁰
[45/-45] _s	6.0	1.37 ⁰	1.69 ⁰
[45/45/-45/-45] _s	6.0	1.56 ⁰	1.69 ⁰
[60/-60] _s	3.0	1.96 ⁰	1.84 ⁰
[60/-60] _s	6.0	1.68 ⁰	1.84 ⁰
[60/60/-60/-60] _s	6.0	1.50 ⁰	1.84 ⁰
[90/90] _s	3.0	0.99 ⁰	1.72 ⁰
[90/90] _s	6.0	2.34 ⁰	1.72 ⁰
[90/90/90/90] _s	6.0	1.70 ⁰	1.72 ⁰